

**GIS TO IMPROVE KNOWLEDGE, MANAGEMENT AND PROMOTION OF
AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL PARK: THE VALORISATION PROJECT OF
UNESCO ETRUSCAN SITE IN CERVETERI, ITALY.**

Authors:

Alessandro Cinnirella, geologist
ECOMedia s.c. – Rome - ITALY
Contact: a.cinnirella@ecomedia.it

Patrick Maurelli, engineer
ECOMedia s.c. – Rome - ITALY
Contact: p.maurelli@ecomedia.it -

Flavio Rosa, engineer
ECOMedia s.c. – Rome - ITALY
Contact: f.rosa@ecomedia.it

Full address: Ecomedia, Via G. Vitelli, 10, 00167, Rome. - tel.fax. +39 06 39737345

Abstract

Within the valorisation project of the Etruscan Necropoli, a UNESCO site in Cerveteri – the ancient Caere city developed between the 9th and 2nd century BC, 40 km far from of Rome – we realised a unique GIS application, called SITAC, that responds to knowledge, project and management needs.

The main project aims to preserve and promote cultural heritage and to grant tourist access to the archaeological, naturalistic and landscape resources: a light electrical train circuit will become the accessibility backbone of this sophisticated complex of more than 500 tombs, often superposed, green areas, viewpoints, almost 5 km of narrows etruscan roads developed in volcanic rocks.

SITAC project started with the 3D analysis performed on recent aerial photos producing an High Resolution DEM (2x2 mt) of the area. The largest part of this area is still under a thick vegetation coverage and many ancient structures have to be excavated.

The project is based on the organization of several thematic layers, vector and raster, in GIS environment. Work proceeded with the integration of different data: survey measurements, dGPS data, photo-interpretation of recent and historical aerial views, historical cartography at different scales, pictures campaign with metrical information and other multimedia documentation.

The integration process has been developed giving a reliability order to the data. We assumed survey measurements as the most accurate ones, on which others data have

been referred and adapted.

Then, the dGPS data, affected by low precision under the vegetation coverage, have been used only for xy mapping while for the z value, we used the surveys points as Ground Control Point (GCP). Again, other features, on different themes, have been referred to the map obtained from survey measurements and dGPS data.

We integrated into the SITAC the information given by the historical cartography, the tombs recognized by photo-interpretation, the tabular data obtained by the archaeological outcrops field classification and the photographic documentation of the site.

The first results of surveying and GIS application are: the tourist paths definition, the definition of alternative routes for a light train, the base maps and vertical views for the execution of primary intervention on the site (cleaning monuments entrances, paths preparation, security and monitoring systems, wood structures, emergency restoration programming).

This sets SITAC as the main system in planning, projecting, evaluating activities concerning the area and as a useful support to decision making processes. The Next step is the GIS integration of the archaeological database, supplied from experts and institutions involved in the project. Georeferencing this documentation is the first step to offer on site the desired descriptions through *mobile devices* and *smart panels* – with texts, maps, pictures, audio files.

This database will be developed referring to three kind of users: 1) expert users for technical purpose: historical analysis, cataloguing, excavation, conservation and restoration plans, risk evaluation; 2) for direct support to tourism, with the full representation of itineraries, facilities and services; 3) remote users, for communication and promotion purpose with interactive and multimedia solutions: virtual tours and museums, cd-rom, webgis application.

Keywords: archaeological sites surveying, Cultural heritage, dGPS mapping, aerial view, Digital Elevation Model, Open source WebGIS.

1. INTRODUCTION¹

The framework in which archeological studies and digital applications circulate is without a doubt multidisciplinary. Ten years ago the database specialist Guimier-Sorbets (1996) had already described the relationship between archeology and computer technology stating that archaeology, like any science, is information management. The three stages in archeological information management are: elaboration of the documents, interpretation, and diffusion of the results as an integration of overall knowledge. Further analysis, synthesis and interpretation will convert these representations into something else thereby risking loss of information. For this reason, as stated by Orlandi (2001), it is necessary to access not only the interpretations produced by the experts but also the primary sources and therefore the original survey data.

¹ This chapter, the chapter 5 and the abstract were written by the three authors together; the rest of the paper was written by Maurelli P. with the exclusion of par. 4.6 written by Cinnirella A..

In reference to archeological and naturalistic sites, the geographical or spatial aspects of the information are particularly important therefore the increase in use of software environments such as DBMS, CAD, GIS and photogrammetrics becomes a necessary step. In archeology, like in many other applications, information storage must be recorded carefully using typologies identification and full description of the documents (metadata).

This said, we believe that in this field the main function of GI systems is to improve the data collection, conservation and diffusion of the information collected through survey activity and document research. The GIS application we are presenting is part of a valorization project at the UNESCO site in Cerveteri – the Etruscan Necropolis “La Banditaccia” in proximity to the ancient Caere city developed between the 9th and 2nd centuries BC, 40 km from Rome (Italy) – and it aims to improve knowledge, management and promotion of an archaeological park.

2. THE VALORIZATION PROJECT OF THE ARCHEOLOGICAL SITE

Within the valorization project at the UNESCO site in Cerveteri the FAEM (Fondazione Archeologica per l'Etruria Meridionale - *the Archeological Foundation for Southern Etruria*) entrusted ECOMedia to undertake the surveys, create the cartography and develop the GIS application for the area, called SITAC (Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico Ceretano - *Cerveteran Archeological GIS Application*). The area of study takes up a large part of the Etruscan necropolis, “La Banditaccia”, excluding the portion which is managed by the local authority for archeological heritage, SAEM (Soprintendenza Archeologica per l'Etruria Meridionale - *Archeological Offices of Southern Etruria*).

The area had been partially excavated during various archeological campaigns in the last century and hundreds of monuments were discovered but remained buried or hidden by vegetation. Many other monuments are still to be located.

Since July 2, 2004, the “La Banditaccia” necropolis, as well as the “Monterozzi” necropolis near Tarquinia, has been included in UNESCO's World Heritage list and was interested by a Management Plan. This plan is a tool that combines the preservation and safeguarding of the Etruscan Necropolises with tourist fruition, accelerating the developmental process in the area. The intention is to improve economic growth and employment in the community by exploiting, as indicated by UNESCO's own statement, the great appeal of the two main archaeological sites in order to promote social and economic development through the enhancement of all tangible and intangible assets diffused over the entire area.

The uniqueness of the site for its historical, cultural and archeological importance is described by UNESCO (2004) as follows: “...the large cemeteries reflect different types of burial practices from the 9th to the 1st century BC, and bear witness to the achievements of Etruscan culture, which over nine centuries developed the earliest urban civilization in the northern Mediterranean. Some of the tombs are monumental, cut in rock and topped by impressive tumuli (burial mounds), others with a wealth of structural details provide the only surviving evidence of Etruscan residential architecture [...]” and town planning schemes.

Many tombs are superposed or still underground, while around them there are green areas, woods, olive plantations, natural landscapes, observation points and paths.

It is important to note that until the start of this valorization project, the entire plateau upon which the necropolis stands was in a state of abandon mainly as a result of insufficient funds for the maintenance and management of the site.

The City of Cerveteri announced an international competition to gather ideas that extended to the entire territory. It stipulated in 2004 an agreement with regional administration and local actors setting into motion the cultural and tourist valorization project for the archeological areas within the municipality. The SITAC GIS initiative was created during project development in conformance with the Management Plan approved by UNESCO.

The valorization project aims to preserve and promote cultural heritage and to grant tourist access to the archaeological, naturalistic and landscape resources of the site: a light-weight electrical train circuit will become the backbone of accessibility of an area that contains thousands of tombs and several kms of Etruscan roads.

The workgroup acquired the guidelines and actions proposed in the Management Plan of the site as shown in the table n.1 making the necessary changes for specific needs. From

the valorization point of view, the strategy is centered on the construction of an IT environment with multiple output possibilities.

Guidelines and Policies for the UNESCO site
<p><u>Systematization of existing data:</u> <i>Collection of cartographic, alphanumeric, photographic, and iconographic data.</i> [...] The first step consisted therefore in collecting this material, classifying it and making it manageable and easy to consult.</p>
<p><u>Development of a GIS and data insertion:</u> [...] an informatized data bank based on the GIS which should link the wide variety of data to the geographical location of each existing tomb or archaeological structure present within the site or included in the buffer zone. [...] This information system will be available through Internet, and it will offer different access levels for researchers and students around the world and for potential visitors to the site.</p>
<p><u>Increasing knowledge of the two necropolises:</u> 1) <i>Continuing excavation activities in the two necropolises.</i> 2) <i>Promoting study initiatives:</i> Knowledge of the two necropolises constantly increases thanks to the large number of studies and research studies carried out. [...]</p>
<p><u>Increasing knowledge of ancient cities:</u> <i>Continuing excavation activities in the ancient cities.</i> Today, the excavations conducted by the Superintendent offices are mainly focused on increasing knowledge on the two ancient settlements.</p>

Table n.1 - Guidelines and policies indicated in the Management Plan (Guido, et al. 2004) and used for the construction of the SITAC.

3. INTERDISCIPLINARY ASPECTS OF THE PROJECT

The question of local expertise is both strategic and transversal to the entire project: from the survey and cartography phases, to the promotional phases, from archeological excavation activities to documenting, cataloguing and restoration, from site cleanup to the safeguard of rare and valuable plants, from cultural promotion in schools to the tourism management. For these reasons, various training courses aimed at increasing qualifications in local manpower were created.

A technical and scientific committee was formed, as was a team of qualified professionals and experts committed to ensuring a dialogue between the analytical phases and the project phases, collaborating in the data collection and the construction of the GIS application.

The site survey was met with many difficulties, the first being. The quality, continuity and completeness of the topographic data acquired with the total station and the GPS were hindered by the flooding of many tombs during the rainy season and by the presence of thick vegetation.

The survey activity also had to take into account the large quantity of tombs that gradually came to light during the 12 months of cleanup handled by FAEM that, in agreement with SAEM, did not include archeological excavations or rather the removal of compact earth over 20 cm in depth. The volunteer groups (organized by FAEM and GAR, *Gruppi Archeologici Romani*) was of invaluable help in removing earth, debris and water from the entranceways of many tombs.

Thanks to these coordinated and parallel activities the first phase of the valorization project in the necropolis was concluded with tangible results in every aspect of the intervention. Much more is still to be done and we hope to receive collaboration from local and international researchers and universities that could continue specific initiatives and studies in the area.

This is the ideal progression in order to foster the convergence of various fields of expertise and the implementation of a collaborative web-based platform using GIS and DBMS

(Budoni, et al. 2003).

4. SURVEY, ANALYSIS AND RESTITUTION OF THE SITE

In the first phase, the workgroup concentrated on the preliminary analysis of the area. In the following paragraphs, we will describe the analytical activity carried out using CAD, GIS and photogrammetry software.

4.1 Geo-cartographic layout of the area

In order to establish a cartographic reference for the entire project area, a suitable IGM95 sub-network was placed with at least 2 plano-altimetric points per hectare depending on the operative phases listed below:

- Retrieval of IGM95 monographs of the points.
- Materialization of network vertexes properly fit with newel posts and/or manholes complete with reference mark.
- Connection to the IGMI network using a GPS and links to existing cadastral maps.

Organization of the SITAC in a GIS environment began with georeferencing four recent orthorectified aerial photographs (IT2000 from the *Compagnia Generale di Parma*, 1:10.000) and four Regional Technical Maps (Regione Lazio, 1:10.000) in overlay, with UTM33 ED50 datum, as a background for the large-scale representations in the SITAC (minor scale of 1:5000). Topographic surveys connected to the IGM95 sub-network and the georeferenced cadastral map were used instead for all hi scale representations.

4.2 Topographic documentation

After various surveys to get an overview of the site were carried out, it was possible to develop a survey campaign project. The campaign was preceded by studies of existing cartography and planimeters in order to locate the main road and paths for tours. Starting from the vertexes of the local georeferenced network to the national IGM95 system, we proceeded by materializing the survey points using metallic benchmarks. The following typologies of points were documented and surveyed:

- **notable points on the longitudinal and transversal profile of the sepulchral road**, in order to create the 3D image and documentation and to develop the ground plan of the area and the route of fruition.
- **notable points of archeological surfacing**, necessary for creating a map of the oriented monuments. Usually these points correspond to the two highest points of entry (intrados) of each tomb and a third point is outside the tomb. These points were used to connect the surveys that followed, including interiors, thereby resolving in this initial phase the positioning and orientation of the 3D space of the structure that was documented photographically.
- **notable points of site morphology** or rather, reference points used to create an initial approximated dimensioned layout of the area necessary for the placement of tombs entrances and fruition routes as well as for site safety management (steps, parapets, handrails, protective covers).
- **photographed points** essential to visual and iconometric documentation. These included points where a tripod was set in front of a tomb entrance and points that were easily recognized in photos of the tombs.

While planning the survey, in addition to budget limitations, we took into consideration the accuracy we desired to meet. Furthermore, in keeping with similar projects (G. Vassena et al., 2000) we chose to make use of various measurement techniques (direct, topographic, photogrammetric) properly integrated into a single reference system because each

technique has its own distinctive characteristics and methods that condition its efficiency in delimited fields while having a margin of interchangeability with each other.

A suitable data handling procedure (postprocessing) can furnish a precision 10-20 cm scale planimeter of the surveyed points with a maximum margin of error of 30 cm in elevation which is considered adequate for the needs of the project. Next we studied the analysis carried out on the sepulchral road and the relative results. For this we used a minimum set of points of the tombs, routes and paths believed to be of importance to the development of the representation model and functional to the layout plans.

At the same time, tables relative to surveyed points and tombs, complete with description, notes and codes for the GIS environment were created.

The basic topographic network structure was made up of over 1200 vertexes: 900 points were placed along the 850-meter-long tract that was analyzed. There were over 200 monuments surveyed in this area with the minimum set of points, and for each one, photographic and iconometric documentation was produced (figure n.1). The most external portion of the route, in sectors with a low density of visible tombs, we were limited to localization and bordering using a GPS.

Figure n.1 – Layout with both zenital and frontal views representing tombs perimeters, entrances and pictures.

4.3 GPS mapping

Taking note of the morphological, natural and archeological complexities of the site in question, we proceeded to an on-site experimental verification of some of the technical and instrumental solutions.

We carried out a survey along the sepulchral road on a 100-meter-long tract with a high level of archeological phenomenon. We were able to verify the limitations in detail and precision by comparing the results we had obtained with the levels necessary for the plan that was to be executed. A reconnaissance of the itineraries planned within the valorization project was carried out using a dGPS in both static mode and dynamic mode, while differential GPS accuracies were obtained on a real-time basis (RT-DGPS) or in Post-Processing (PP-DGPS). GPS stationary survey posed 5-15 minutes stations and dynamic survey had the antennae at a constant distance from the ground. The most significant results from this experiment included the quantification of survey activity necessary for the

requested cartography and the location of criticalities in topographic and iconometric documentation. These informations were useful for the correct programming of the campaign; in fact, the evaluations of the experiment led us to tackle the survey by introducing a mixture of techniques and inserting data and metadata in a single GIS/DBMS environment right from the start.

Here is a list of the vectorial themes in the SITAC gathered through dGPS mixed techniques:

- limits of preexisting boundaries on the site;
- tuffaceous borders that delimit the sepulchral road on both sides;
- secondary paths along the centerline;
- centerlines for the variations of the route proposed during the preliminary project phase;
- Perimeters of vegetation;
- perimeters of some large monuments or tomb complexes in dGPS dynamic mode;
- notable points needed in order to control the quality of the data in dGPS stationary mode.

The integration process was developed giving data a reliability order. We assumed survey measurements to be the most accurate on which other data was referred and adapted. The dGPS data, affected by low precision, was used only for xy mapping while for the z value, we used the survey points as a Ground Control Point (GCP).

4.4 Photographic and iconometric documentation

The iconometric survey was aimed at producing semimetric and georeferenced photographic images essential in producing quick documentation of the Etruscan assets. The images were associated to notable topographic features recognizable in them. Oriented with a 3D attitude graphic system and rendered semimetric through the calculation of control measurements, they were elaborated in order to extract documents as follows:

- profiles along the first linear sector of intervention with frontal views in GIS environment.
- graphics necessary to create an initial promotional product that can be used via Internet or multimedial CD-ROMs.
- project documentation used for the safeguarding of archeological assets and during the safety management phase.

The photographs of monuments were taken following fixed criteria (frontal view, distance and optical notes, vertical stadia rod positioned in the focal point of the photo) that allowed for storage of the main metric references on the digital image obtained.

It's interesting to note that every photo inserted in the SITAC was referred to on the cartographic plan both by the object photographed (a polygon) and by the position of shooting (a point) that generally corresponds to the point of view of a potential visitor along the itinerary. The photographs can be consulted by clicking on the feature using a traditional hotlink function. The same photos were georeferenced using z-values in a frontal view with an x axis that represents the metric progression of the site's itinerary route (figure n.1).

With regards to monuments that present a significant amount of flat surfaces, we are testing photogrammetry softwares Winrefran (*AeC2000*) and PhotoModeler (*Eos Systems Inc.*) that orthorectifies and scale items on pictures beginning from the recognition of a few vertical and horizontal lines. This is important in order to obtain images of the facades of the monuments that the requirements of the dimensional analysis and the restitution of objects in 3D environment.

The monuments and other relevant elements can be documented with any number of photos, and, for example, were used to keep track of successive maintenance phases monitoring the progress of valorization. This was proven invaluable in the frequent cases where topographic control piquets were lost. The entrances were often obstructed by earth or unfit for use due to rainwater stagnation. Using the series of photographs organized by the DB, it was possible to document these situations and hypothesize interventions by

indirect analysis. A complete photographic documentation was produced to represent and analyze the entrances into the numerous tombs that face the sepulchral road. Indeed we were able to measure the apertures and therefore estimate the thickness of the obstructions to be removed.

4.5 Map documentation

For portions of the necropolis, some cartography relative to previous archeological surveys were used: the first was carried out by Raniero Mengarelli around 1933 in occasion of work done on the new access road to the site (Cosentino, 1995), another one was carried out more recently and offers a detailed description of a group of tombs, some of which were superimposed vertically in the tuffaceous bank. These cartographic thematics were vectorized and georeferenced in the SITAC and is an upgraded documentation of great interest especially due to the representations of the interiors of the tombs that had been excluded from the initial phase of the survey.

But the GIS application on existing cartography that sparked the greatest interest was the analysis of historical aerial photographs. A series of historical aerial photographs (images of 1943, 1944, 1945, and 1962 obtained from the ICCD [aerial photographic national archives](#)) was georeferenced in a GIS environment and photo-interpretation led to the design of approximately 500 locations where monuments were presumed to lie.

It's not a novelty that the buried structures are highlighted by the micro-morphology and vegetation that cover them, and analyzing the traces in aerial photos produces results that are often satisfying to spot archeological assets. The verification on ground was crucial and had to be done systematically using the right amount of manpower and time required for the extensive reconnaissance of the sites.

During the first phase, the design of these traces or presences was limited to an approximate but georeferenced perimeter (figure n.2). Later, the evidence will be evaluated and measured. The interpretation of traces and anomalies had to be accompanied by GPS technology in order to have a comparison perimetry in a short amount of time.

The identification of the traces was not limited only to the indisputably relevant evidence in the aerial photographs, but the presumed archeological presences that can be identified by less clear signs were also catalogued in GIS environment. The notes inserted in the DB will constitute the memory of these distinctions. In regards to the cataloguing of traces and anomalies as highlighted by Caprasecca (2004), the convenience of using a DBMS archive lies in having an open structure available and in continuous mutation in which the definition of traces and anomalies can be organized with newer, more detailed headings because the base classification system requires adjustments specific to the territory being investigated.

The superimposition of flights taken in different eras enabled the evaluation of the territorial transformations caused by natural and/or anthropological phenomenon.

Figure n.2 – Overlay mapping of tombs recognition: in green the traces from aerial views, in blu the surveyed monuments, in red the main project route.

4.6 3D Restitution

The over 900-point survey with centimetric precision in x, y, and z allowed for the three dimensional restitution of the sepulchral road and the entrances to the tombs (figure n.3). It is a simplified representation and a basis for constructing a photorealistic three-dimensional model. Regarding two relevant monuments - “Del Grifo” tombs and the area of the “Moretti” tumulus - the topographic points were increased in number in order to obtain a detailed model of the Etruscan assets (figures n.3 and n.4).

Interesting to note among the developments along this line are the passage from the digital model of the present state to the reconstruction of the historical landscape and the augmented reality. All representations were georeferenced in the SITAC and the overall output of the various morphologies was reproduced (figure n.4). In fact, a 3D digital model of the entire study area of the “La Banditaccia” plateau was recreated from four stereoscopic aerial photographs from *flight IT2000* (CGR, Parma). Through digital photogrammetric techniques, we created a model of the interior correlation that took into account the reciprocal position of the various photograms as well as the radial distortion values caused by the lens used.

After defining the interior correlation model using an adequate number of tie points (25 per couple), we moved on to define the exterior correlation model using GCP (Ground Control Point) emissions relative to the regional technical cartography (CTR, 1:10.000 scale). With the two correlation models defined, epipolar images of the stereo couples were produced. From these the DEM (Digital Elevation Model) of the area was extracted with a 2m x 2m resolution. The model represents the realistic state of the surface of the terrain including the elements that lay on top (buildings, vegetation, etc.).

Figure n.3 – DEM of the necropolis plateau and 3D views.

Figure n.4 – 3D models of two relevant monuments along the proposed itinerary.

Morphological analysis of the digital model of the terrain showed that the plateau on which the necropolis was built extends for about 40ha with a slight SW incline (about 3%). To the sides of the plateau there are two prominent incisions: one is S shaped and runs NE-SW along which flows the “Manganello” ditch, and the other is manmade (etruscan) on which a large portion of the necropolis stands. The shape of these incisions bordering the tuffaceous plateau, suggest a natural origin: grooves were made from running water on the surface that eroded the tuff on the plateau producing steep, incised slopes that stop at the argillaceous

substratum and result stratigraphically lower to the tuffaceous lithology (red tuff with black scoriae). Regarding the incision to the north, it is reasonable to deduce that where the sepulchral road now runs, at one time there was a flow of water that, due to natural or artificial causes, offered its bed as the construction site for the tombs that are found here today.

In order to obtain the DTM (Digital Terrain Model) some corrections were made to the DEM. The area where the most significant corrections were made included the woods that border on the roads and sepulchral road. With the help of botanical specialists, existing arboreal typologies are to be identified so we could estimate the heights and density of the vegetation. By calculating the average heights of the trees and the surface extension of the vegetation, we can obtain the values to subtract and the area upon which to apply the corrections. Through a simple conditional analysis in GIS environment on these themes, we will obtain the model for the terrain.

4.7 Design and development of the SITAC

The great irregularity of the tuffaceous artifacts, the size of the necropolis, and the fact that most of the monuments were still buried became the main reasons for developing an instrument to gauge the continuous sedimentation of knowledge of the site. Creating a database (DBMS) and the SITAC (GIS) responds also to the need of partial but concrete results within the budget allotted by the Regional Administration in this initial phase. It is important to note that by using more expensive 3D survey techniques, like the laser scanner, we would have obtained a more detailed restitution limited to few monuments that would have been disadvantageous to the extensive knowledge and representation of the site.

It is also true that a topographic survey of a number of points on the monuments would have reduced the resources that were otherwise used for the photographic documentation and the GPS survey. It is evident that in the next project phases we could increase the topographic control points and obtain a more accurate layout of the monuments.

The systematic cataloguing of cultural and artistic assets and the organization of the DB were carried out in compliance with ministerial standards (ICDD, 2004) and monument coding was defined in collaboration with archeological authorities. Different digital formats converged in the SITAC: raster (*tif, jpg, ecw*), vectorial (*dxf* and *shp*) and multimedial (digital videos, audio and presentations).

The aims of this tool are manifold:

- A. **collection of reproducible cartographic bases** with the possibility of exporting in manageable digital and paper formats;
- B. **strategic environment analysis** through GIS functions that support the analytical and evaluative process and in particular can integrate the morphological, archeological, geologic, geotechnical, hydrological, vegetational, and urban aspects.
- C. Improving **project of the interventions**, excavations or valorizations, with the possibility of obtaining early layout scenarios useful for the preliminary evaluation of impact and costs/benefits.
- D. Supplying an **operative tool for the georeferenced documentation of activities** to the various operators in the field: used for cataloguing the archeological assets but also essential for micro planning, measuring and perimetrating, and to monitor the transformations.
- E. **multimedial documentation of the archeological and naturalistic assets of Cerveteri** made available in a software environment that manages various formats -audio, video (figure n.5), graphic and textual - useful in activities regarding training and research, environmental awareness and communication, and cultural and tourist promotion.

Figure n.5 – Clip from the digital movie to support the valorization project presenting the idea of visiting the site by light electrical train.

One of the innovative elements of the SITAC GIS application was the creation of frontal views that represent vertical projections or vertical sections of the structural sequence. In these views, the metrics of the ordinate (y) represented the actual elevation (z-values) whereas the horizontal axis (x) represents the progressive distances along the rectified fruition tract. It follows that this was no longer a traditional overlay of maps in GIS environment but “vertical maps” of topics that contained information on elevation and that in other layouts of the project were displayed in planimetry.

This passage, although intuitive in its interpretation, was quite laborious. Another merit of this representation was the use of the tables listing the various thematics, or characteristics, to connect the two typologies of views; planimetric and vertical: for example the tomb entrances that were represented in the planimetry by segments made by joining the two highest points of the entrance and taken with centimetric precision, were also shown as a vertical theme, over the rectified profile view, as polygons where height and elevation respected the relative data.

Similarly, the high points of the monuments and archeological phenomena were projected onto suitable vertical planes and so it was possible to anchor frontal images of these monuments using control points just as in a planar view. With this approach it was possible to represent the complex sequence of the facades of the monuments on both sides of the sepulchral road (figure n.6).

Within the limits induced by the orthorectification of the photos, the result was also of metric interest with regards to the architectural elements that were on the same plan as the topographic control points.

The connection between the planimetric and vertical thematic allowed for extremely dynamic navigation of SITAC information and for quick organization of useful and understandable paper output (map/prospect). This relationship function of features in the two views was used to manage objects, while the traditional join functions based on table - usually external - systematically update and add information to the SITAC with a simple operation.

Figure n.6 – Part of the layout presenting vertical profile by topographic survey and photo mosaic processing.

At present, the points, profiles and perimeters taken on-site using GPS and topographic surveys were implemented into the SITAC and 3D models were created. The use of GIS also guaranteed the creation of maps necessary for planning the interventions meeting all dynamic, updating, multi-scale and metric precision requirements.

Among the mid-term project scenarios, by introducing multimedial technological specifications and a networked infrastructure on the area, a client-server GIS can also manage:

- Monitoring the sites in terms of risk and vulnerability in addition to surveillance and security management;
- The creation of on-site audiovisual services for tourist consulting the multimedial documentation.

4.8 Quick Survey Kit for archeological findings and structures

In order to help and improve the activities relating to investigation, excavation and planning, the operators were given a field equipment kit: a set of instruments and procedures for georeferencing, quick surveying and positioning of archeological findings or other phenomenon. This necessity tied in well with the goal of gradually creating an *intelligent map of the locations*. Its *intelligence* derived from two factors: the mapping valorizes the expertise that collaborated on analyzing the site and it was also implemented in a highly interactive computer system. The kit was available on-site and consisted of a case containing all the necessary equipment for georeferencing recovery points, monument surveying and initial data cataloguing.

5. CONCLUSION

The survey activity was used towards the fruition route of the UNESCO site but also to produce the altimetric characterization of the area creating a topographic network in a georeferenced framework system. The post-elaboration of topographic and iconometric data led to the definition of a series of GIS themes. Around two monuments a 3D model

was created and used to develop intervention prototypes geared towards safeguarding, safety and accessibility.

The first step of the planning phase defined the layout designed for tourism purposes and alternative routes for a backbone of fruition of the necropolis including a noninvasive and removable railway circuit that can host a light-weight electric train. Planning the valorization interventions on the monuments was based on three primary criteria: visibility, accessibility and protection from water.

The printouts necessary for communicating the progress of the project were created and integrated into the SITAC GIS application. The tables included three series of printouts: a series of tables for the analysis of the site, a series pertaining to development insertions, and a concise, project-analytical series of tables.

From this point of view, it was possible to verify the efficiency of the printout arrangement in a single cartographic, multi-thematic and multi-scale environment in particular when deciding the optimal route (screening the project variables). The itinerary had to meet various criteria-objectives tied to the choice of how to pave the railway circuit for the transit of a rubberwheeled train. The criteria was listed by importance as follows:

1. slope inferior to 13%,
2. avoid transit over buried archeological presences,
3. avoid crossing areas occupied by rare and valuable vegetation,
4. guarantee the best fruition and visibility of the site by a visitor along the itinerary,
5. guarantee a curvature of the vehicle with a minimum 7 meter range,
6. place an adequate number of stops.

The SITAC integrate iconometric and topographic elements for layouts that can be used by archeologists in direct surveys. The map restitutions and the multimedial documentation collected also offered efficient cultural and tourist promotional support, including videos and various photographic mosaics.

A synthesis of the SITAC dedicated to the archeological sites in the Cerveteri area will be published on Internet through the implementation of an open-source Map Server. The development of the Map Server within a larger Web publication foresees data distribution via Internet, both on the public side of the website, as a promotional tool for cultural heritage, and through intranet applications with accounting on request. This choice supports a many-to-many distribution of informations using an open and networked database (Dangermond, 2001). The Web-GIS has to be conceived as a collaborative platform for research and diffusion and to produce benefits for the technical and scientific community as well as for the network of cultural promoters and tour operators.

The SITAC proved to be a good solution for sedimentation and knowledge sharing for the various operators involved: archeologists, tour operators, cultural promoters, tourists, and decision-makers in administrative bodies.

The main results obtained so far thanks to the use of GIS were:

- dimensional and directional analysis of the archeological entrances used primarily by design teams and archeologists.
- Support to the development and evaluation of the interventions starting from the screening of the variables of the main fruition route.
- The geographic identification of the perimeters with a 3-meter range of precision including suspected archeological presences through the study of historical aerial views.
- 3D models of the plateau (curves at 2 meters) and of two valuable monument complexes (with 20 cm precision).

These conclusions can be extended to all cases of valorization of archeological sites in general where GIS based solutions can support the following activities:

- Planning and management of excavation campaigns, from locating archeological phenomena to site surveys;
- Representations of routes and tourist fruition spaces of the site with scenario simulation of accessibility and mobility;
- Extension of the 3D representation to 4D, with a time variable, of historical landscapes or project layout scenarios (scoping).
- Promotional output products presenting services and fruition and tourist itineraries of an archeological-natural park.

- Virtual tours via Internet or CD-ROM in pseudo-3D environments and scenarios of *augmented reality*, where it is possible to associate the documentation of the artifacts (displaced in museums) and the areas or monuments of origin.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The agreement that foresees the drawing up of a definitive valorization project of the site and the development of the SITAC was stipulated in 2005 within a service conference between the following: the City of Cerveteri, Regione Lazio, which raised funds, the Archeological Offices of Southern Etruria (SAEM - *Soprintendenza Archeologica per l'Etruria Meridionale*), the Archeological Foundation for Southern Etruria (FAEM - *Fondazione Archeologica per l'Etruria Meridionale*) and Galatour, a local tourist agency. The project design and the SITAC was entrusted to FAEM who nominated the architect Virgilio Bocchini to head the project and created a team, in which ECOmedia is part, to cover all the necessary areas of expertise.

All the data, including the photographic material and the monument cataloguing was used towards the final project which was delivered to the city council and to archeological authorities. Local authorities are engaged to obtaining new resources in order to continue the executive project phases and to execute further surveys particularly regarding the construction of service buildings.

REFERENCES

- Budoni, A., De Bonis, L., Maurelli, P. (2003), *Metodi e procedure di valutazione nell'architettura di un sistema informativo interattivo di supporto alla gestione ed elaborazione di strumenti e processi di pianificazione a livello comunale*, AIV congress proceedings, Milano, Italy, <http://www.valutazioneitaliana.it/documenti/milano/Budoni-De-Bonis-Maurelli.zip>
- Caprasecca, A. (2004), *il ruolo della foto aerea storica nello studio del paesaggio antico*, Dipartimento di Archeologia e Storia delle Arti dell'Università degli Studi di Siena – Dottorato XX Ciclo, Grosseto, Italy.
- Cosentino, R. (1995), *Cerveteri e il suo territorio*, edizioni Quasar, Rome, Italy.
- Dangermond, J. (2001), *g.net-A New GIS Architecture for Geographic Information Services*, ESRI ArcNews, vol. 23, n 1, <http://www.esri.com/news/arcnews/>
- Guido, M.R., Ferroni, A.M, Capodaccia, S. (2004), *Etruscan necropolis of Cerveteri and Tarquinia, Management plan*, BAC Ministry press, Rome, Italy, pp. 44-45.
- Guimier-Sorbets, A. M. (1996), *Le traitement de l'information en Archéologie: archivage, publication et diffusion*, Les nouvelles de l'archéologie, n°63, pp.10-13.
- ICCD (2004), *standard catalografici*, Normativa SIGEC ver. 3.00, BAC Ministry, Rome, Italy, <http://www.iccd.beniculturali.it/standard/>
- ICOMOS (2004), *advisory body evaluation, site nomination of Cerveteri and Tarquinia*, UNESCO, Paris, France, <http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1158>.
- Orlandi, T. (1999), *Multimedialità e archeologia*, in Archeologia e Calcolatori, Ed. all'Insegna del Giglio, Firenze, Italy, No. 10, pp. 145-157
- Vassena, G. et al. (2000), *Il rilevamento finalizzato al progetto di conservazione. Il caso della torre dell'antica rocca di Sergnana*, Stampato in proprio, Brescia, Italy.